

Strategic Management and Its Effect on Achieving Excellence among Leaders Working in Al-Quds Insurance Company

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to reveal the effect of strategic management in achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company. The researcher used the descriptive approach, and the study sample consisted of (80) leaders working in Al-Quds Insurance company. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used a questionnaire to measure strategic management, and a questionnaire To measure the achievement of excellence, both of which were prepared by the researcher, and the study reached a set of results, the most important of which are: that the level of strategic management applied by the leaders working in Al-Quds Insurance company (80.1%) is divided into two dimensions: after the strategic direction, it got the first place with a relative weight (82. %), and after developing human capital, it ranked second with a relative weight of (78.6%), while the level of achieving excellence by the leaders working in Al-Quds Insurance company reached (79.1%). The study also revealed a relationship between the total degree of strategic management and the Achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company, and it was found that there is a significant impact of the overall degree of the strategic management scale on the satisfaction of the beneficiaries in the company. Al-Quds Insurance company, and it was found that there is a significant impact of the overall degree of the strategic management scale on human resources in Al-Quds Insurance company, and the study showed that there are statistically significant differences between the degrees of strategic management among the leaders working in Al-Quds Insurance company due to the educational qualification variable in favor of the bachelor's degree, and the study showed There were no statistically significant differences between the degrees of strategic management among the leaders working in Al-Quds Insurance company due to the variable years of experience, and the study showed the absence of statistically significant differences between the degrees of achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds Insurance company due to the variable (educational qualification, years of experience), and the researcher recommends paying attention to the development of strategic goals in the organization, and the participation of workers in building strategic goals and visions, and selecting qualified workers and employing them in positions that suit their abilities and capabilities.

KEYWORDS: Strategic management, excellence, strategic direction, Human capital development, Al-Quds insurance company.

1. THE GENERAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

1.1. Introduction:

The world has witnessed new transformations brought about by globalization and developments in the technological reality in all its aspects, which has affected all aspects of life, especially the aspect of work and business. Institutions need to adapt to the new reality in light of the material and human resources they contain to ensure their continuity in this reality, which is characterized by abundance fluctuations and intensification of competition.

In order for organizations to adapt to the changes taking place around them, they need administrative patterns that help in unleashing the latent energies within their employees, providing them with opportunities to search for new in the field of work, and continuous updating of work systems in line with the surrounding changes in the work environment (Saad, 2020: 3).

Human resource management is one of the most important administrative functions in the organization or facility, and it is no less than other functions such as marketing, production and finance, given the importance of the human element and its impact on the productive efficiency of the organization. The concept of human resource management expanded to include various activities within the organization to include analysis and description of jobs and attracting and attracting resources Humanity and its Motivation (Ben Imara and Marati, 2019: 177).

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Distinguished management is the one that can achieve the desired goals, and works on building a set of human relations among its members, and works to achieve management distinction among workers, but excellence is not in one aspect at the expense of another, but in all components in order to give an integrated picture of the gaps that may affect the performance of the organization (Al-Zahrani, 2019: 173).

The pursuit of excellence in any institution is a basic requirement and a necessity of administrative development, which requires these institutions to adopt an intellectual style and an administrative philosophy that depends on an approach related to how to achieve tangible results for the organization to achieve the budget in satisfying the needs of all parties, stakeholders or society as a whole (Al-Rasheed, 2009): 114).

Based on the foregoing, this study came to examine the impact of strategic management in achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds Insurance company.

1.2. Study problem and questions:

A number of studies, such as the study of Ben Emara and Marati (2019) have recommended to conduct more research in the areas of applying strategic management, which is an effective element in developing organizations in general and the skills of individuals in particular, and enables the business organization to develop the human element in a way that enables it to distinguish itself from competitors in the market, as Abdo's study (2017) indicated the same recommendation. In light of that, the researcher, through this study, wants to identify the level of strategic management practice and its role in achieving excellence among employees. The problem was formulated through the following main question:

What is the impact of strategic management with its dimensions (strategic guidance and human capital development) in achieving excellence in its dimensions (beneficiary satisfaction, human resources) among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company?

The following sub-questions are derived from the main question:

- 1- What is the level of strategic management applied by the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company?
- 2- Is there an impact of strategic management in its two dimensions (strategic direction and human capital development) on the satisfaction of beneficiaries among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company?
- 3- Is there an impact of strategic management in its two dimensions (strategic direction and human capital development) on the human resources of the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company?
- 4- Are there statistically significant differences in the respondents' answers about "the impact of strategic management in achieving excellence among leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company due to the following variables (years of experience, university qualification)?"

1.3. Objectives of the study:

The study aims to:

- 1- Identifying the level of strategic management practice among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company.
- 2- Studying the impact of strategic management in achieving excellence among employees of Al-Quds insurance company.
- 3- To reveal the extent to which there are statistically significant differences in the respondents' responses about the impact of strategic management in achieving excellence among employees of Al-Quds insurance company due to the following variables (years of experience, educational qualification).

1.3. Study hypotheses:

The first main hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant effect at the α (α) 0.05 level of strategic management in achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company

The following hypotheses emerge from this hypothesis:

- 1- There is a statistically significant effect at the α (0.05) level of strategic management with its dimensions (strategic guidance, human capital development) on the satisfaction of beneficiaries among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company
- 2- There is a statistically significant effect at the α (0.05) level of strategic management with its dimensions (strategic direction, human capital development) on the human resources of the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company

The second main hypothesis:

There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha < 0.05$) between the degrees of strategic management among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company with regard to demographic variables (educational qualification, years of experience).

The third main hypothesis:

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There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha < 0.05$) between the degrees of achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company with regard to demographic variables (educational qualification, years of experience).

1.4. Study model:

The researcher developed the study and its dimensions shown in Figure (1) based on the problem of the study in accordance with the relevant previous studies that were reviewed. The researcher has developed the model for the study, which is shown as follows:

Figure (1): Study model: prepared by the researcher based on the studies shown in Table No. (1):

Table (1). Study model

References and sources approved	variable
(Abu Jomaa and Al-Hamidi, 2021), (Rizk Allah and Misak, 2018), (Abdo, 2017), (Jabbara, 2017)	Independent variable Strategic management
(Al-Zahrani, 2019)	Dependent variable Achieving Excellence

1.5 procedural definition:

First: Strategic Management:

The researcher defines it procedurally: it is a system of diverse and integrated processes that are concerned with analyzing the organization from the inside and outside and formulating appropriate methods, their application and evaluation, and the degree

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of strategic management is measured by the total degree of the responses of the study sample members to the tool that was prepared for this purpose.

Second: Strategic direction:

The researcher defines it procedurally: the long-term aspirations of the institution towards its vision, and raising the level of ambitions of the employees within the institution. It is measured by the degree obtained by the study sample members on the strategic direction in the study tool.

Third: Human Capital Development:

The researcher defines it procedurally: the proper selection of the workforce within the institution, and work to raise the level of its capabilities and capabilities, and it is measured by the degree obtained by the study sample members after developing the human capital in the study tool.

Fourth: Achieving Excellence:

The researcher defines it procedurally: those administrative procedures carried out by the leaders working in the insurance company, to provide distinguished services and high-quality outputs within the company to serve the workers and consumers.

Fifth: Satisfaction of the beneficiaries:

The researcher defines it procedurally: the beneficiaries' satisfaction with the services they receive from them during their dealings with the company, from the point of view of the leaders working in the company, and it is measured by the degree obtained by the study sample members on the dimension of the beneficiaries' satisfaction in the study tool.

Sixth: Human Resources:

The researcher defines it procedurally: the company's human resources' awareness of the importance of the beneficiaries' satisfaction as a criterion for evaluating their work, as well as the extent of their knowledge of the administrative, organizational, administrative and electronic aspects, from the point of view of the company's working leaders, and it is measured by the degree obtained by the study sample members on the human resources dimension in the study tool.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Strategic management

The concept of strategic management:

As he defined it (Morsi and Selim, 2017: 11): it is a set of decisions and actions related to the formation and implementation of strategies designed to achieve the objectives of the organization.

And I defined it (Ayoub, 1997: 428): It is that process that consists of a set of steps through which the senior management analyzes the existing opportunities and threats, the strengths and weaknesses of the company, defines the mission and goals, then sets strategies at the company level, implements them and exercises strategic control.

And he defined it (Awad, 2013: 6): It is the process that ensures the design, implementation and evaluation of decisions with long-term impact that aim to increase the value of the organization from the point of view of customers, shareholders and society as a whole.

And I knew it (Al-Arif, 2016: 6): It is the science and art of forming, implementing and evaluating interrelated functional decisions that enable the company to achieve its goals.

Definitions varied and varied, and the definition of a creator was not reached, as a result of the multiplicity of angles from which each researcher looked, as well as the difference in viewpoints, and this is normal in the humanities, but is considered a positive indicator.

Dimensions of strategic management Strategic management includes the following dimensions (Abdo, 2017: 40-43)

1- Determining the strategic direction: It is for the organization to be able to define a long-term strategic direction and vision, and it is usual for that vision to extend between five to ten years in the future.

2- Investing in competitive capabilities: It is for the institution to invest and develop its individual capabilities in various functional fields to implement its strategies.

3- Human capital development: It is for the institution to employ those with qualifications and abilities in positions they deserve, and to work on developing these capabilities and capabilities through workshops and courses.

4- Supporting organizational culture: It is a set of beliefs, ideologies, central and core values, symbols, rules, customs, and traditions shared by all employees in the facility, and which affects the way the facility conducts its operations.

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5- Emphasis on ethical practices: It is noticeable that the effectiveness of the strategy's implementation processes increases if it is built on the basis of ethical practices, and that establishments with the necessary ethics encourage their employees to be ethical, and emphasize ethical practices that enable them to choose the appropriate ethical pattern at all levels the organization.

6- Implementation of balanced control: the control process is necessary to ascertain the extent to which enterprises achieve the results they wish to achieve regarding strategic competition and high returns. Oversight helps managers in the decision-making process.

The second topic: achieving excellence:

Excellence concept:

Excellence is defined as outstanding practice in managing work and achieving results (Al-Salma, 2012: 8). Gardens (2011: 145-147) also sees that the term excellence has a moral concept, which is frequently mentioned in the writings of Greek philosophers, and carries different meanings, and the opinions of thinkers and scholars who have experience in the Arabic and English languages differ on this concept, some of them suggested superiority, and some of them suggested Tabriz, Excellence and success, and others suggested eminence, in addition to that, the term excellence refers to status because it is the translation of the word used internationally after practical institutions were established bearing the phrase "Centre of Excellence." Scholars used the term "Center of Excellence" to translate it into Arabic as "distinguished centers." And His Excellency.

Excellence concept:

It is known (Al-Buhaisi, 2014: 9) that the company's performance exceeds the expected performance, whether from the company itself or its peers, or it exceeds the expectations of customers.

While Al-Shrooqi (2018: 13) defines him as the company's continuous excellence by demonstrating the best practices in performing its tasks and services.

And from the point of view (Ivancvich, 1997: 28) that it is the pursuit of the highest level of performance that can be achieved by the employees of the company.

(Ragheb, 2011: 60) indicates that achieving excellence is achieving the desired goals, the ability to build a set of human relationships among its members, the promotion of teamwork spirit, the possibility of providing appropriate conditions for the performance of work, and taking into account individual differences when distributing work.

He defines it (Al-Jabari, 2009: 8) as the outcome of the application of a set of criteria that enable the organization to reach unprecedented competitive results in increasing its competitive strength.

It is defined by (Al-Salami, 2007, 13) a case of administrative creativity and organizational excellence that achieves extraordinary levels of performance.

It also enables the importance of achieving excellence in that it is considered a necessity of development in order to improve performance levels, by improving the experiences and capabilities of employees in the company, containing and motivating them, so that each employee feels that the company is his property and thus achieves his loyalty to it. Achieving excellence is related to the quality of work and the amount of service provided by employees in the company, and therefore we can say that the importance of achieving excellence lies in achieving measurable results such as time savings and improved service quality to prove that the company is looking for ways to become more effective and successful (Hanieh, 2016: 20).

The researcher defines achieving excellence as: those administrative procedures carried out by the leaders working in the insurance company, to provide distinguished, high-quality services and outputs within the company to serve the workers and consumers.

Dimensions of achieving excellence:

1- Beneficiaries' satisfaction: It is through the institution's acquaintance with the opinion of the external beneficiary (the service recipient) in its services to meet their needs in an appropriate manner, as this is one of the most prominent evaluation and follow-up mechanisms, as well as investigating opportunities that the business institution can benefit from (the Arab Organization for Administrative Development).

2- Human resources: It is the knowledge and awareness of the employees in the organization of all administrative practices and works, and the knowledge of the importance of the various factors that affect the satisfaction of the beneficiaries, and affect their development and distinction.

3- Electronic management: It is the employees' knowledge of the aspects of electronic management that pertain to their business, and contribute to facilitating the provision of services to beneficiaries, and documenting business.

4- Administrative and organizational management: It is the employees' knowledge of the administrative and organizational aspects related to their jobs in the company, and doing them to the fullest extent (Al-Zahrani, 2019: 190).

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The relationship between strategic leadership practices and achieving excellence:

Strategic leadership plays an active role in achieving excellence in institutional performance through its ability to transform the organization from a state of disintegration and decline to leadership and excellence. Outstanding performance is based on defining the direction and strategic planning in building a sound and solid foundation for all its components to achieve the goals of the organization, and allows it to conduct Organizational analysis and updating on a regular basis, with the aim of achieving performance excellence (Abdo, 2017: 81).

The ingredients for the success of excellence must include focusing on supporting the skills, capabilities, and capabilities of human resources as they are the source of creativity and innovation, in addition to revealing the pivotal and basic capabilities in the organization, and trying to manage these capabilities that characterize the organization, in a way that achieves the added value for it and for stakeholders (Gad Al-Rub, 2013: 19).

2.2. Previous studies

The first axis: studies that dealt with strategic management.

The study of Abu Jumaa and Al-Hamdi (2021) aimed to measure the impact of strategic leadership on achieving competitiveness in the Al-Nabil Food Industries Company in Jordan. The researchers used the descriptive analytical approach, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers used a questionnaire to collect data from the study sample, and the study sample consisted of (950) An employee of Al-Nabil Food Industries Company in Jordan, and the study reached a set of results, the most important of which are: There is an impact of strategic leadership in achieving competitiveness in Al-Nabil Food Industries in Jordan.

While Al-Haroun study (2019) aimed to identify the degree of strategic management practice among college deans in private Jordanian universities in the capital, Amman, and its relationship to competitive advantage from the point of view of department heads and faculty members. The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used the first two questionnaires to measure the degree of the practice of strategic management, and the second to measure the degree of availability of competitive advantage, and the study sample consisted of (269) heads of departments and faculty members at Middle East University, Al-Zaytoonah University, Al-Isra University and the University of Petra. The results of strategic management were high, and the results showed a positive and significant correlation between the degree of strategic management practice and the degree of competitive advantage. The results also showed that there were statistically significant differences in the degree of strategic management practice due to the variable of sex and in favor of males, and for years of service, and it was in favor of less than 5 years. And college specialization in favor of scientific colleges.

While the study of Al-Hilali and Al-Sayed (2018) aimed to identify the entrance to strategic management and the requirements for its application in Mansoura colleges, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used the descriptive analytical approach. The degree of importance, and also found that there are substantial differences between the degree of importance and the degree of availability in determining the strategic goals of the college in favor of importance.

Tabidi (2018) study aimed to identify the impact of strategic management on the efficiency and effectiveness of performance in the Sudanese telecommunications sector, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used the descriptive analytical approach, and the study reached several results, the most important of which are: that there is a strong correlation between the personal and demographic variables of the respondents, knowledge and familiarity with concepts and methods Strategic management, as well as the need to address the obstacles and determinants that affect the application of strategic management in the telecommunications sector.

Jabara study (2017) aimed to measure the impact of strategic leadership on improving the performance of insurance companies in Jordan. The researcher used the descriptive analytical method. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used a questionnaire. The study sample consisted of (12) companies selected according to the percentage of paid compensation, and the sampling unit consisted of (207) factor of managers and heads of departments working in the mentioned companies, and the study reached a set of results, the most important of which are: the presence of a high level of efficiency in adopting strategic leadership and improving performance in insurance companies in Jordan, and the presence of a significant and statistically significant impact of strategic leadership on improving the performance of companies Insurance in Jordan.

The second axis: studies that dealt with achieving excellence.

The study of Murzuqlal (2020) aimed to identify the role of organizational culture in achieving the outstanding performance of university library workers "a field study in the university library in M'sila". The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used a questionnaire, and the study sample consisted of (50) male and female workers. The study reached a number of results, the most important of which are: that organizational culture contributes greatly to achieving outstanding performance, and this is reflected in the improvement in performance and adaptation to the

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internal and external factors of the library and thus participation in the exchange of opinions and ideas, which is reflected positively on the services provided by the library, and this is what it leads to gaining the satisfaction of the beneficiaries.

While the study of Al-Mutairi and Al-Fadhli (2020) aimed to identify the reality of human capital leadership towards achieving administrative excellence at the University of Jeddah. The researchers used the descriptive survey method. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers used the questionnaire as a research tool, and the study sample consisted of (100) female workers. A set of results, the most important of which are: that the study sample members were neutral in their approval of the reality of human capital leadership towards achieving administrative excellence at the University of Jeddah, and the results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the respondents' responses towards the reality of human capital and its relationship to administrative excellence due to the variable years of experience.

The study of Samara et al. (2020) aimed to identify the role of school administration in achieving cultural excellence among students of public secondary schools in Jordan and Palestine from the point of view of their principals, and to achieve the objectives of the study, researchers used the descriptive analytical approach, and the study consisted of 220 principals and directors in secondary schools in Palestine and Jordan, and the study reached several results, the most important of which are: The role of school administration in achieving cultural excellence among students in public secondary schools in Jordan and Palestine from the point of view of its principals came to a large extent, and it also found that there are no differences in the sample estimates for the role of school administration in achieving excellence. The cultural level among students in public secondary schools in Jordan and Palestine according to state variables, academic qualifications and years of experience.

The study of Saad (2020) aimed to identify transformational leadership and its role in achieving institutional excellence, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used the descriptive analytical approach, and the study sample consisted of 177 employees. Which came with a high degree of approval, and also found a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of transformational leadership and the achievement of institutional excellence in the vocational education sector in Lebanon.

While the Al-Buhaisi study (2020) aimed to identify the role of empowering workers in achieving institutional excellence, a field study on technical colleges in the governorates of the Gaza Strip. For several results, the most important of which are: There is a statistically humiliating relationship between organizational culture, administrative delegation, sharing information and work teams on the one hand, and between leadership, human and service excellence on the other hand, and it also found a statistically significant relationship between empowerment in achieving institutional excellence due to the gender variable and in favor of males.

Al-Zahrani's study (2019) aimed to reveal the degree of availability of total quality management requirements and their relationship to administrative excellence among the leaders of Al-Baha schools from the teachers' point of view. It includes administrative excellence, and the study sample consisted of (341) teachers from Al-Baha region in Saudi Arabia. Public education in Al-Baha region for administrative excellence came to a significant degree of achievement, and the study showed a positive correlation between total quality management and administrative excellence.

The study of Ben Amara and Marati (2019) also aimed to show the role of strategic management of human resources in achieving excellence. The study seeks to try to identify the most important functions of strategic management in relation to the human element and how to achieve excellence for the organization. The researcher used the descriptive and inductive approach. The study concluded that Strategic management of the human element enables the business organization to develop the human element in a way that enables it to distinguish itself from competitors in the market.

The study of Rizkallah and Misak (2018) aimed to determine the role of strategic management of human resources in achieving administrative excellence in light of the new changes that the era has witnessed. Or to a certain strategic situation that allows achieving competitive advantage, and this means the need for institutions to search for intellectual wealth, skills, and creative and innovative ideas that are inherent in their untapped human competencies where they can invest in them, to extract higher value through their development and transformation into sustainable competitive advantages. Fundamental to the survival of the enterprise in the field of competition.

What distinguished the current study: the selection of a new sample that was only studied by a powerful study (2017), and this is within the limits of the researcher's knowledge. It also addressed the impact of strategic leadership and achieving excellence among senior leaders. Leaders working in insurance companies.

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3. STUDY METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Methodology:

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used the descriptive approach, through which he tries to find out the relationship between the variables of the study and the analysis of its data, the relationship between its components, the opinions that are raised about it, the processes it contains, and the effects it causes, where the descriptive analytical approach is defined as the approach through which the description of the phenomenon is the subject. The study and analysis of its data and a statement of the relationships between its components and the opinions raised about it and the processes it contains and the effects it causes (Abu Hatab and Sadiq, 2010, 104).

3.2 Study Limits:

1. Objective limits: strategic management and its impact on achieving excellence in the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company.
2. Temporal limits: The study covers the time-limited 2021.
3. Spatial limits: This study was conducted on the Al-Quds insurance company.
4. Human limits: the working leaders in the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company.

3.3 Study population and sample:

The study population consists of all the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company, whose number is about (100) leaders, according to the official records, according to the company's latest statistic for this year.

As for the study sample: it consisted of the exploratory sample: a survey sample of (30) workers from the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company was distributed, and they were chosen by the simple random method, in order to verify the psychometric measures of validity and reliability of the scale and to verify its validity to measure the subject of the study. And the actual sample: the study sample consisted of (80) workers from the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company, and they were chosen by the intentional method, and it was found through the results that 80.0% of the sample members had a bachelor's degree, while 17.5% had a diploma, and 2.5% had a scientific qualification Postgraduate. It was also found through the results that 60.0% of the respondents have years of experience less than 5 years, 13.8% between 5-10 years, and 26.3% have 10 years or more.

3.4 Study Tools:

The researcher built the following study tools, which are:

1. The strategic management scale prepared by the researcher: in its initial form, it consists of (13) phrases consisting of two axes (defining strategic direction (6 paragraphs), human capital (7 paragraphs)).
2. The scale of achieving excellence prepared by the researcher: in its initial form, it consisted of (12) phrases, and it consisted of two axes (beneficiaries' satisfaction (6 items), human resources (6 items)).
3. The statistical treatments used in the study: The researcher used the "Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)" program.

The following statistical methods were also used:

1. Percentages, frequencies, and relative weight. This is mainly used for the purposes of knowing the frequency of the categories of a variable, and it is used to describe the sample of the researched study, and to answer the first and third question.
2. Cronbach's Alpha as well as the split-half test; to know the stability of the paragraphs of the questionnaire.
3. Pearson Correlation Coefficient; to measure the degree of correlation, this test is based on studying the relationship between two variables, and it was used to calculate the internal consistency, the structural validity of the questionnaire, and the relationship between the variables.
4. One sample t test; to measure if the arithmetic mean of the dimensions is equal to the mean degree.
5. One way ANOVA; to measure the difference between the arithmetic averages of the dimensions for the three variables or more.
6. Simple Linear Regression Analysis: Linear Simple Regression to predict the degree of the dependent variable through the degree of the independent variable.
7. Multiple linear regression analysis to predict the degree of the dependent variable through the degree of the independent variables.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Study questions:

The first question: What is the level of strategic management applied by the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company?

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To identify the level of strategic management among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company, the researcher calculated the averages, standard deviations, and the relative weight of the resolution degrees, and the results are shown as follows: The arithmetic mean of the degrees of strategic management among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company reached (52.1) degrees, with a deviation Standardized (6.5) degrees, and the relative arithmetic weight reached (80.1%), and this indicates that the level of strategic management applied by the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company is high.

As for the two dimensions, it ranked first after determining the strategic direction with a relative weight of 82.0%, followed by the development of human capital with a relative weight of 78.6%.

The researcher attribute this to the existence of a long-term vision within the company according to a careful analysis of the company's external and internal environment, and that this vision depends on reality and real data, in addition to the flexibility of the vision and its ability to develop and renew to suit reality, requirements of the environment and the changes that occur, in addition to that it seeks to implement strategies that That would be compatible with its goals and strategic vision, through the development of human capital within the company, and this development is done through training courses and the provision of appropriate financial capabilities that contribute to this development.

The second question: What is the level of achievement of excellence by the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company?

To identify the level of achievement of excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company, the researcher calculated the averages, standard deviations, and the relative weight of the resolution degrees, and the results are shown as follows: The arithmetic mean of the degrees of achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company reached (47.5) degrees, with a deviation Standardized (5.6) degrees, and the relative arithmetic weight reached (79.1%), and this indicates that the level of achieving excellence applied by the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company is high.

As for the two dimensions, it ranked first after human resources with a relative weight of 79.4%, followed by the satisfaction of beneficiaries with a relative weight of 78.9%.

The researcher attributes this to the fact that the company's employees have high knowledge of the importance of the beneficiaries' satisfaction in their work, and that their satisfaction is an important criterion for evaluating their work within the company, and that they know the importance of developing their administrative and organizational capabilities within the company because of its reflection on their performance at work, so that they are able to deal with the beneficiaries as required, and contribute to the beneficiaries getting what they came for with high quality and quickly.

4.2 Testing and discussing the hypotheses of the study:

The first main hypothesis: there is a statistically significant correlation at the level of significance ($\alpha < 0.05$) between strategic management and achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company?

To verify the validity of this hypothesis, a matrix of Pearson Correlation Coefficients was found to identify the nature of the relationship between strategic management and achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company, and the results related to this hypothesis are shown in the following table: Statistical significance ($p\text{-value} < 0.01$) between the total degree of strategic management and the achievement of excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company, and this indicates that the higher the level of application of strategic management, the more this leads to a rise in the level of achieving excellence among the leaders working in the Jordanian company. Al-Quds for insurance and vice versa.

It was found that there was a direct statistically significant relationship ($p\text{-value} < 0.01$) between the degrees of (determining strategic direction, developing human capital) and (beneficiary satisfaction, human resources) among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company.

The researcher attributes this to the fact that if there is a clear strategic vision based on data and accurate analysis of the company's internal and external environment, in addition to the flexibility of this vision and goals in line with reality and developments, the company's employees are convinced of this vision and goals, and the selection of employees based on their capabilities and high potential, Continuous training and development, and giving them the powers that facilitate their job tasks, which is reflected in achieving excellence through the workers' knowledge of the aspects of their administrative and organizational work, knowledge of the most important aspects on which they will be evaluated, and their continuous quest for development and knowledge in order to complete the beneficiaries' transactions faster, and complete them easily and to ensure that they receive their services with the best quality at the most appropriate price.

The current study agreed with the Tabidi study (2010) that the application of strategic management contributes to raising the efficiency and effectiveness of performance in telecommunications companies. It also agreed with the study of Zarqallah and Misak (2018) on the role of strategic management in achieving administrative excellence.

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The first sub-hypothesis: there is a significant effect of statistical significance at the level of significance ($\alpha < 0.05$) for the degrees of strategic management on the satisfaction of beneficiaries with Al-Quds insurance company.

To identify the impact of strategic management (the independent variable) on the degrees of satisfaction of beneficiaries (the dependent variable) at Al-Quds insurance company, a simple linear regression analysis (Enter) was used, and to identify the impact of the dimensions of strategic management (determining strategic direction, developing human capital). (Independent variable) on the degrees of satisfaction of the beneficiaries (the dependent variable) at Al-Quds insurance company, multiple linear regression analysis (Stepwise) was used. The results are illustrated through the following table: A significant effect of statistical significance was found for the total degree of the strategic management scale on the satisfaction of beneficiaries in the company. Jordan French Insurance, the model explained 52.5% of the total variance in the degree of satisfaction of the beneficiaries, while the remaining percentage, which is 46.5%, is due to other factors, where the coefficient of determination of the model was 0.525, and through the results shown in the previous table, it was found that the coefficients of the regression model are a function Statistical, and the linear regression equation that helps predict the degrees of (beneficiary satisfaction) with the knowledge of the degrees of (strategic management) can be formulated as follows:

Beneficiary satisfaction = 0.38 (strategic management)

From the previous equation, it was found that the higher the level of strategic management by one degree, the more this would lead to a 0.38 degree increase in the degree of beneficiaries' satisfaction with Al-Quds insurance company.

The following variables from the dimensions of strategic management (determining strategic direction, developing human capital) were entered into the model, and the second step was stopped, where it was found that the following variables are statistically significant and have an impact on the forecasting model (determining strategic direction, developing human capital), which are: arranged according to the strength of its impact on the degrees of satisfaction of the beneficiaries. The model explained 52.6% of the total variance in the degree of satisfaction of the beneficiaries, while the remaining percentage, which is 46.4%, is due to other factors, where the coefficient of determination of the model was 0.526, and through the results shown in the previous table it was found The coefficients of the regression model are a statistical function, and the linear regression equation that helps predict the degrees of (beneficiary satisfaction) with the knowledge of the degrees (determining strategic direction, developing human capital) can be formulated as follows:

Beneficiary satisfaction = 0.49 determination of strategic direction + 0.30 development of human capital.

From the previous equation, it was found that the higher the level of determining the strategic direction by one degree, the higher this would lead to a 0.49-degree beneficiary satisfaction degree with Al-Quds insurance company, and the higher the level of human capital development by one degree, the higher the degree of satisfaction of beneficiaries. With a score of 0.30 at Al-Quds insurance company.

The researcher attributes this to the application of strategic management within the company through appropriate, appropriate and flexible strategic directions that are renewed based on developments and changes, selecting and employing scientific competencies, training the company's employees, paying attention to developing their capabilities and functional capabilities, giving them the powers and authorities that contribute to the completion of their work, and providing capabilities The materiality of the employees in order to develop them and facilitate the process of serving the beneficiaries, all this positively affects the satisfaction of the beneficiaries on the quality and speed of the services they receive, and their comfort in dealing with the employees and their obtaining what they came for the company for. The employees are highly qualified and well trained, and who apply the goals and vision of the institution and they seek to achieve it, and those who belong to this institution and its vision, all of this affects the quality of the services they provide to the beneficiaries, which affects their level of satisfaction with these services they receive.

The second sub-hypothesis: There is a significant effect of statistical significance at the significance level ($\alpha < 0.05$) for the degrees of strategic management on human resources at Al-Quds insurance company.

To identify the impact of strategic management (the independent variable) on the degrees of human resources (the dependent variable) at Al-Quds insurance company, a simple linear regression analysis (Enter) was used, and to identify the impact of the dimensions of strategic management (determining strategic direction, developing human capital). (Independent variable) on human resources degrees (dependent variable) at Al-Quds insurance company, multiple linear regression analysis (Stepwise) was used. The results are illustrated through the following table: A significant effect of statistical significance was found for the overall degree of the strategic management scale on human resources in Al-Quds insurance, the model explained 32.9% of the total variance in the degree of human resources, while the remaining percentage, which is 77.1%, is due to other factors, where the coefficient of determination of the model amounted to 0.329, and through the results shown in the previous table, it was found

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that the coefficients of the regression model are a function Statistical, and the linear regression equation that helps predict the degrees of (human resources) given the degrees of (strategic management) can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{Human Resources} = 9.7 + 0.30 (\text{Strategic Management})$$

From the previous equation, it was found that the higher the level of strategic management by one degree, the more this would lead to a 0.30 degree increase in the human resources degree at Al-Quds insurance company.

The following variables from the dimensions of strategic management (determining strategic direction, developing human capital) were entered into the model, and the first step was stopped, where it was found that the following variables are statistically significant and have an impact on the prediction model (human capital development) and are arranged according to the strength of their impact On human resources degrees, the model explained 31.1% of the total variance in human resources degrees, and the remaining 78.9% is due to other factors, where the coefficient of determination of the model amounted to 0.311, and through the results shown in the previous table it was found that the coefficients of the regression model Statistical function, and the linear regression equation that helps predict the degrees of (human resources) with the knowledge of degrees (human capital development) can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{Human Resources} = 12.79 + 0.40 \text{ Human Capital Development}$$

From the previous equation, it was found that the higher the level of human capital development by one degree, the higher this would lead to a 0.40 degree increase in the degree of human resources at Al-Quds insurance company.

The researcher attributes this to the clarity of the vision and goals of the company and the company's attempt to convince its employees of these goals, by stating these goals and making them realistic based on the company's capabilities, making them flexible and changing according to the company's external and internal developments, and working to employ workers with high capabilities and capabilities, and work on training and developing them, giving them the appropriate powers to perform their jobs, and promoting distinguished workers, all of this contributes to the production of workers who know their job duties well, and know the importance of the beneficiaries' satisfaction in their work, and make them aware of the administrative and organizational aspects of their work, and make them keen to be familiar with everything related to their job. The company's interest in them enhances their interest in their job and themselves in order to be able to perform their jobs in the best way.

The second hypothesis: There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha < 0.05$) between the degrees of strategic management among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company with regard to demographic variables (educational qualification, years of experience)?

To find the differences between the degrees of strategic management among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company with regard to demographic variables (educational qualifications, years of experience), one way ANOVA was used, the results are illustrated through the following tables:

Regarding the educational qualification variable: it was observed that there were significant differences with statistical significance ($\alpha < 0.01$) in the strategic management of the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company with regard to the educational qualification, and to find the dimensional differences the LSD test was used, where it was found that the evaluation of the application of strategic management among certificate holders The bachelor's degree is lower than the diploma and postgraduate holders, and these differences are statistically significant, while there are no substantial statistically significant differences between the other groups. Regarding the variable years of experience: It was noted that there were no significant differences with statistical significance ($\alpha > 0.05$) in the degrees of strategic management among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company with respect to the number of years of experience.

The researcher attributes the existence of differences in the educational qualification variable in favor of the bachelor in the application of strategic management to the extent of knowledge possessed by the holders of the bachelor's degree compared to the diploma, as the years of study are more, which makes them study specialized subjects more and more deeply, which resulted in their knowledge of the importance of strategic management and its impact on the development of capabilities. The employees and the development of the strategic direction of the company, making them apply this type of management in order to reach the goals they wish to achieve, and the absence of differences in favor of higher studies is due to the fact that the number of workers with a higher degree than a bachelor's degree is employed, in contrast 64 workers with a bachelor's degree, the reason for the existence of differences attributed to the bachelor's variable may be due to the large number of bachelor's degree holders compared to diploma and graduate studies.

The current study differed with Abdo's study (2017) in the absence of differences in the practice of strategic leadership due to the educational qualification variable.

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The researcher also attributes the absence of differences in the variable years of experience in applying strategic management to the fact that the company selects employees with high capabilities and competencies, in addition to the company implementing courses and involving employees in them, which raises their capabilities and capabilities, and contributes to the transfer of experiences among employees, which contributes to reducing the gap between the new workers and the old ones, and the presence of a developed work environment with clear goals contributes to making the work environment cooperative, which contributes to the transfer of experiences and the cooperation of workers in order to complete the work entrusted to them, considering that they are one work team and their goal is one, and accordingly their application to management the strategy is similar.

The current study differed with the study of Al-Haroun (2019) in the presence of differences in the practice of strategic management due to the variable years of experience in favor of less than 5 years.

The third hypothesis: There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha < 0.05$) between the degrees of achievement of excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company with regard to demographic variables (educational qualification, years of experience)?

To find the differences between the degrees of achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company in relation to the demographic variables (educational qualifications, years of experience), the one-way ANOVA test was used. The results are shown in the following tables:

Regarding the educational qualification variable: it was noted that there were no significant differences of statistical significance ($\alpha > 0.05$) in the degrees of achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company in relation to the educational qualification.

Regarding the variable years of experience: It was noted that there were no significant differences with statistical significance ($\alpha > 0.05$) in the degrees of achieving excellence among the leaders working in Al-Quds insurance company with respect to the number of years of experience.

The researcher attributes the absence of differences in both the educational qualification variable and the years of experience in achieving distinction, to the company's success in developing the capabilities of its employees, through their selection and then training, development, and promotion, and through the development of strategies and goals that employees believe within the institution, so they are cultivated within employees have a spirit of excellence, regardless of their academic qualifications and years of experience. By training them, providing the appropriate capabilities for their work, and giving them powers, they contribute to making them at one level of knowledge, which increases their enthusiasm for excellence and demonstrates their capabilities. Achieving excellence is not linked to experience or qualifications. As far as it is related to the employees' affiliation to work and their belief in what they do.

The current study agreed with the study of Al-Mutairi and Al-Fadhli (2020) in the absence of differences in achieving excellence due to the variable years of experience.

STUDY RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1- Al-Quds insurance company and all other companies must take attention to the development of strategic objectives in the institution.
- 2- Al-Quds insurance company and all other companies must enhance the participation of employees in building strategic goals and visions.
- 3- Al-Quds insurance company and all other companies must improve operation of selecting employees to build efficiency and employing them in positions that suit their abilities and capabilities.
- 4- Al-Quds insurance company and all other companies must improve training employees' programs and methods to develop their capabilities on an ongoing basis.
- 5- Al-Quds insurance company and all other companies must enhance distinguished and creative workers within the company.

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